

A NOTE ON FIBONACCI NUMBERS OF EVEN INDEX

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Abstract

We introduce a representation of the integers based only on Fibonacci numbers of odd index. Then we give an elementary combinatorial proof of the fact that a positive integer n is a Fibonacci number of even index if and only if $\langle n\varphi \rangle + \frac{1}{n} > 1$.

1. Introduction

The Fibonacci numbers are recursively defined from $F_1 = F_2 = 1$ by $F_{n+2} = F_{n+1} + F_n$, for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. We say that m is a Fibonacci number of even (resp. odd) index if there exists an even (resp. odd) number n such that $m = F_n$.

In the rest of the paper, we denote by φ the so called “golden section”, i.e., $\varphi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$. For all $x \in \mathbb{R}$, we denote by $\langle x \rangle$ and by $\lfloor x \rfloor$ the fractional and the integer part of x , respectively. Clearly $\langle x \rangle = x - \lfloor x \rfloor$.

Some characterizations of the Fibonacci numbers of even and odd index appear in the literature. In [2], Herrmann showed a property related to the local minima/maxima of the sequence of fractional parts of multiples of the golden section. More precisely, ([2], Theorem 2.3), n is a Fibonacci number of even index if and only if $\langle n\varphi \rangle > \langle i\varphi \rangle$ for all $1 \leq i < n$, while it is a Fibonacci number of odd index if and only if $\langle n\varphi \rangle < \langle i\varphi \rangle$ for all $1 \leq i < n$. A completely different characterization is stated in [1]: n is a Fibonacci number if and only if $5n^2 + 4$ or $5n^2 - 4$ is a square and, more precisely, n is a Fibonacci number of even index if and only if $5n^2 + 4$ is a square (see [3]).

In this note, we introduce a representation of the integers based only on Fibonacci numbers of odd index, which differs from the well known Zeckendorf representation (see [7]). Then, we prove a characterization for the Fibonacci numbers of even index. From a result of Möbius (see [4]), we deduce the corresponding condition for the odd case.

2. Preliminaries

In [7], Zeckendorf proved that any positive integer can be represented uniquely as the sum of one or more distinct Fibonacci numbers in such a way that the sum

does not include any two consecutive Fibonacci numbers. We observe that, under some assumptions, we can restrict such a sum only to Fibonacci numbers of odd index. Namely, every positive integer has a (not unique) ternary decomposition of the following form.

Proposition 1 (Fibonacci odd index ternary representation). *Let n be a positive integer, then it can be written in the form*

$$n = \sum_{h=0}^s a_h F_{2h+1} \tag{1}$$

for some $s \geq 0$ with $a_0 \in \{0, 1\}$, $a_h \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ for $0 < h < s$ and $a_s \in \{1, 2\}$. In this case, we write $n = (a_0 \dots a_s)$. In the sequel, we will refer to such representation simply as “the representation of n ”.

Proof. The property easily follows by applying an algorithm of successive divisions starting from the greatest Fibonacci number of odd index less or equal than n . \square

The procedure above gives a “normal representation”, but in general such representation is not unique, e.g., $41 = (1222) = (01101)$ and $F_9 = (00001) = (1112)$. It is clear that, as we start from the greatest Fibonacci number of odd index less or equal than n , the normal representation for n is the longest representation of n . Nevertheless, there is an interesting class of integers for which we can prove the uniqueness.

Proposition 2. *Every Fibonacci number of even index has the unique representation $(1 \dots 1)$.*

Proof. Let $n = F_{2m}$. Then n has the representation $(1 \dots 1)$ of length m , which is the longest representation of n . Suppose $(a_0 \dots a_h)$, with $h \leq m - 1$, is a different representation of n . If we perform the element-wise difference between the two representations, we get the non-zero string $(b_1 \dots b_{m-1}) = (a_0 \dots a_h) - (1 \dots 1)$ with $b_i \in \{-1, 0, 1\}$, for all $0 \leq i \leq m - 1$. Then we have $\sum_{i=0}^{m-1} b_i F_{2i+1} = 0$. Now, let $A = \{i \in [0, m - 1] \mid b_i = 1\}$ and let $B = \{i \in [0, m - 1] \mid b_i = -1\}$. Obviously $A \neq B$. From the previous equation, we get $\sum_{i \in A} F_{2i+1} = \sum_{i \in B} F_{2i+1}$, which is absurd, as, from [7], every positive integer is represented uniquely as the sum of nonconsecutive Fibonacci numbers. \square

The next two propositions recall some known properties of Fibonacci numbers.

Proposition 3 ([5], identity 28; [6], p. 52). *Let n be a positive integer, then:*

$$F_n \varphi = F_{n+1} + (-1)^{n+1} (\varphi - 1)^n, \tag{2}$$

and

$$F_n \varphi + F_{n-1} = \varphi^n. \tag{3}$$

Proposition 4. *Let n be a positive integer, then*

$$\lfloor F_n \varphi \rfloor = \begin{cases} F_{n+1}, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd;} \\ F_{n+1} - 1, & \text{if } n \text{ is even.} \end{cases}$$

Proof. Identity 103b of [6] states that $F_{n+1} - F_n \varphi = \frac{(-1)^n}{F_{n-1} + F_n \varphi}$. From the identity (3) and observing that $\frac{1}{\varphi} = \varphi - 1$, we have $F_n \varphi = F_{n+1} - (1 - \varphi)^n$, and then the thesis. \square

From the previous propositions immediately follows the next.

Proposition 5 ([2], Lemma 2.1). *Let n be a positive integer, then*

$$\langle F_n \varphi \rangle = \begin{cases} (\varphi - 1)^n, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd;} \\ 1 - (\varphi - 1)^n, & \text{if } n \text{ is even.} \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

A direct consequence of the previous is the following inequality.

Proposition 6. *Let r, s integers such that $1 \leq r \leq s$. Then*

$$\sum_{h=r}^s \langle F_{2h+1} \varphi \rangle < (\varphi - 1)^{2r}. \tag{5}$$

Proof. From the equality (4), and observing that $(\varphi - 1)^2 - 1 = 1 - \varphi$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{h=r}^s \langle F_{2h+1} \varphi \rangle &= \sum_{h=r}^s (\varphi - 1)^{2h+1} = (\varphi - 1)^{2r+1} \sum_{h=0}^{s-r} (\varphi - 1)^{2h} \\ &= (\varphi - 1)^{2r+1} \frac{((\varphi - 1)^2)^{s-r+1} - 1}{(\varphi - 1)^2 - 1} = (\varphi - 1)^{2r+1} \frac{1 - (\varphi - 1)^{2s-2r+2}}{\varphi - 1} \\ &= (\varphi - 1)^{2r} \langle F_{2(s-r+1)} \varphi \rangle < (\varphi - 1)^{2r}. \end{aligned}$$

\square

3. Main Result

Before proving the main result, we need to observe that every representation $(a_0 \dots a_s)$ of a positive integer n belongs to one of the following six types:

- (1) $a_0 = 0$, $a_i \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ for all $1 \leq i < s$, and $a_s \in \{1, 2\}$;
- (2) $a_i = 1$ for all $0 \leq i \leq s$;
- (3) $a_i = 1$ for all $0 \leq i < s - 1$, $a_{s-1} = 0$, and $a_s = 1$;
- (4) $a_i = 1$ for all $0 \leq i < s - 1$, $a_{s-1} = 0$, and $a_s = 2$;

- (5) there is r with $1 \leq r < s - 1$ such that $a_i = 1$ for all $0 \leq i < r$, $a_r = 0$, $a_j \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ for all $r < j < s$, and $a_s \in \{1, 2\}$;
- (6) there is r with $1 \leq r \leq s$ such that $a_i = 1$ for all $0 \leq i < r$, $a_r = 2$, $a_j \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ for all $r < j < s$, and $a_s \in \{1, 2\}$.

For example, the representations $(1212 \dots 12)$ and $(122 \dots 2)$ are of type (6), while (111012) is of type (5). We can now prove the main result by analyzing the six types above, recalling that, from Proposition 2, n is a Fibonacci number of even index if and only if its representation is of type (2).

Theorem 1. *Let n be a positive integer. Then n is a Fibonacci number of even index if and only if $\langle n\varphi \rangle + \frac{1}{n} > 1$.*

Proof. Let $(a_0 \dots a_s)$ be a representation of n . We analyze the six cases above and prove that only in case (2) we have $\langle n\varphi \rangle + \frac{1}{n} > 1$.

- (1) Let $a_0 = 0$. Then

$$\langle n\varphi \rangle = \left\langle \sum_{h=1}^s a_h F_{2h+1}\varphi \right\rangle \leq \sum_{h=1}^s a_h \langle F_{2h+1}\varphi \rangle \leq 2 \sum_{h=1}^s \langle F_{2h+1}\varphi \rangle,$$

and from the inequality (5) it follows that

$$\langle n\varphi \rangle < 2(\varphi - 1)^2 < \frac{4}{5}.$$

If $n \geq 5$, then $\langle n\varphi \rangle + \frac{1}{n} < 1$. By direct calculation, the same inequality also holds for $n = 2$ and $n = 4$.

- (2) Let $a_0 = \dots = a_s = 1$. In this case $n = F_{2m}$ for some m . From the identity (4), we have $\langle n\varphi \rangle = \langle F_{2m}\varphi \rangle = 1 - (\varphi - 1)^{2m}$, while from the identity (3) we have $F_{2m} < F_{2m}\varphi + F_{2m-1} = \varphi^{2m}$. Then

$$\langle n\varphi \rangle + \frac{1}{n} > 1 - (\varphi - 1)^{2m} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{2m}} = 1 - (\varphi - 1)^{2m} + (\varphi - 1)^{2m} = 1.$$

- (3) Let $a_0 = \dots = a_{s-2} = 1$, $a_{s-1} = 0$ and $a_s = 1$. Then, from the identity (5), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \langle n\varphi \rangle &= \langle (F_{2s-2} + F_{2s+1})\varphi \rangle \leq \langle F_{2s-2}\varphi \rangle + \langle F_{2s+1}\varphi \rangle \\ &< 1 - (\varphi - 1)^{2s-2} + (\varphi - 1)^{2s+1}. \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, from the identity (4) we have

$$n = \sum_{h=0}^{s-2} F_{2h+1} + F_{2s+1} = F_{2s-2} + F_{2s+1} > F_{2s-2} + F_{2s-1}\varphi = \varphi^{2s-1},$$

i.e., $\frac{1}{n} < \left(\frac{1}{\varphi}\right)^{2s-1} = (\varphi - 1)^{2s-1}$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle n\varphi \rangle + \frac{1}{n} &< 1 - (\varphi - 1)^{2s-2} + (\varphi - 1)^{2s+1} + (\varphi - 1)^{2s-1} \\ &= 1 - (\varphi - 1)^{2s+2} < 1, \end{aligned}$$

where in the last step we used the identity $1 - (\varphi - 1)^3 - (\varphi - 1) = (\varphi - 1)^4$.

(4) Let $a_0 = \dots = a_{s-2} = 1$, $a_{s-1} = 0$ and $a_s = 2$. We proceed analogously to the previous case. From the identity (5), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \langle n\varphi \rangle &= \langle (F_{2s-2} + 2F_{2s+1})\varphi \rangle \leq \langle F_{2s-2}\varphi \rangle + 2\langle F_{2s+1}\varphi \rangle \\ &< 1 - (\varphi - 1)^{2s-2} + 2(\varphi - 1)^{2s+1}. \end{aligned}$$

From the identity (4), we have

$$n = \sum_{h=0}^{s-2} F_{2h+1} + 2F_{2s+1} = F_{2s-2} + F_{2s-1} + F_{2s+2} > F_{2s-1} + F_{2s}\varphi = \varphi^{2s},$$

i.e., $\frac{1}{n} < \left(\frac{1}{\varphi}\right)^{2s} = (\varphi - 1)^{2s}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \langle n\varphi \rangle + \frac{1}{n} &< 1 - (\varphi - 1)^{2s-2} + 2(\varphi - 1)^{2s+1} + (\varphi - 1)^{2s} \\ &= 1 - (\varphi - 1)^{2s+2} < 1, \end{aligned}$$

where in the last step we used the identity $1 - 2(\varphi - 1)^3 - (\varphi - 1)^2 = (\varphi - 1)^4$.

(5) Let $a_0 = \dots = a_{r-1} = 1$, $a_r = 0$ for some $1 \leq r < s - 1$, $a_j \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ for $r < j < s$, and $a_s \in \{1, 2\}$. Then

$$n = \sum_{h=0}^{r-1} F_{2h+1} + \sum_{h=r+1}^s a_h F_{2h+1} = F_{2r} + \sum_{h=r+1}^s a_h F_{2h+1}. \tag{6}$$

From the previous equation, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \langle n\varphi \rangle &= \left\langle \left(F_{2r} + \sum_{h=r+1}^s a_h F_{2h+1} \right) \varphi \right\rangle = \left\langle F_{2r}\varphi + \sum_{h=r+1}^s a_h F_{2h+1}\varphi \right\rangle \\ &\leq \langle F_{2r}\varphi \rangle + 2 \sum_{h=r+1}^s \langle F_{2h+1}\varphi \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

From the identity (4) and the inequality (5), we get

$$\langle n\varphi \rangle < 1 - (\varphi - 1)^{2r} + 2(\varphi - 1)^{2r+2}.$$

Coming back to the equation (6), remembering that in this case $s \geq r + 2$ and having in mind the identity (3), we have

$$n \geq F_{2r} + F_{2r+5} = F_{2r} + F_{2r+2} + 2F_{2r+3} > F_{2r+2} + F_{2r+3}\varphi = \varphi^{2r+3},$$

i.e., $\frac{1}{n} < (\varphi - 1)^{2r+3}$. Then

$$\langle n\varphi \rangle + \frac{1}{n} < 1 - (\varphi - 1)^{2r} + 2(\varphi - 1)^{2r+2} + (\varphi - 1)^{2r+3} = 1,$$

where in the last step we used the identity $2(\varphi - 1)^2 + (\varphi - 1)^3 = 1$.

(6) Let $a_0 = \dots = a_{r-1} = 1$, $a_r = 2$ for some $1 \leq r \leq s$, $a_j \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ for $r < j < s$, and $a_s \in \{1, 2\}$. Proceeding as in the previous case, we have

$$n = \sum_{h=0}^{r-1} F_{2h+1} + 2F_{2r+1} + \sum_{h=r+1}^s a_h F_{2h+1} = F_{2r+3} + \sum_{h=r+1}^s a_h F_{2h+1}.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \langle n\varphi \rangle &= \left\langle \left(F_{2r+3} + \sum_{h=r+1}^s a_h F_{2h+1} \right) \varphi \right\rangle = \left\langle F_{2r+3}\varphi + \sum_{h=r+1}^s a_h F_{2h+1}\varphi \right\rangle \\ &\leq \langle F_{2r+3}\varphi \rangle + 2 \sum_{h=r+1}^s \langle F_{2h+1}\varphi \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

From the identity (4) and the inequality (5), we get

$$\langle n\varphi \rangle < (\varphi - 1)^{2r+3} + 2(\varphi - 1)^{2r+2} \leq (\varphi - 1)^5 + 2(\varphi - 1)^4 < \frac{2}{5}.$$

Then, as $n > 1$, we have $\langle n\varphi \rangle + \frac{1}{n} < 1$. □

From the following result of Möbius [4], we easily obtain the characterization for the Fibonacci numbers of odd index.

Theorem 2 ([4]). *Let n be a positive integer. Then n is a Fibonacci number if and only if the real open interval $(n\varphi - \frac{1}{n}, n\varphi + \frac{1}{n})$ contains exactly one integer.*

Corollary 1. *Let n be a positive integer. Then n is a Fibonacci number of odd index if and only if $\langle n\varphi \rangle - \frac{1}{n} < 0$.*

Proof. Let $\langle n\varphi \rangle - \frac{1}{n} < 0$, $m = \lceil n\varphi - \frac{1}{n} \rceil$ and suppose $n > 1$. From the hypothesis, $\langle n\varphi - \frac{1}{n} \rangle = \langle n\varphi \rangle - \frac{1}{n} + 1$ and then

$$n\varphi - \frac{1}{n} = \left[n\varphi - \frac{1}{n} \right] + \left\langle \varphi - \frac{1}{n} \right\rangle = m - 1 + \langle n\varphi \rangle - \frac{1}{n} + 1 = m + \langle n\varphi \rangle - \frac{1}{n} < m.$$

On the other hand,

$$n\varphi + \frac{1}{n} = n\varphi - \frac{1}{n} + \frac{2}{n} = m + \langle n\varphi \rangle + \frac{1}{n} > m,$$

and then the interval $(n\varphi - \frac{1}{n}, n\varphi + \frac{1}{n})$ contains exactly one integer, so n is a Fibonacci number. Moreover

$$\langle n\varphi \rangle + \frac{1}{n} = \langle n\varphi \rangle - \frac{1}{n} + \frac{2}{n} < \frac{2}{n} < 1,$$

and, by Theorem 1, it does not have even index. Conversely, suppose $n = F_{2m+1}$. From the identity (4), $\langle F_{2m+1}\varphi \rangle = (\varphi - 1)^{2m+1}$, and from the well known Binet's formula (see [6], p. 52) we have $F_{2m+1} = \frac{\varphi^{2m+1} + (\varphi-1)^{2m+1}}{\sqrt{5}}$. Then, with some straightforward calculation, we get

$$\langle F_{2m+1}\varphi \rangle - \frac{1}{n} = (\varphi - 1)^{2m+1} - \frac{1}{F_{2m+1}} = (\varphi - 1)^{2m+1} - \frac{\sqrt{5}}{\varphi^{2m+1} + (\varphi - 1)^{2m+1}} < 0.$$

□

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